

CELL PHONES AND TEXT MESSAGING IN CLASSES: SOLUTIONS TO DEAL WITH COMMON PROBLEM IN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Azimova Maftuna Shuxrat qizi

Master Student at UzSWLU.

Roziya Usmonova

Scientific advisor.

Abstract.

English language classes now enjoy wide accessibility to the technology sources which has already resulted in the emergence of mobile assisted language learning environment. However, it is an undeniable fact that students in current classes tend to overuse mobile phones and text messaging in a way that often causes disruptive misbehavior in lessons. This article tries to offer some solutions for teachers to create effective language learning environment by nourishing positive student behavior in language classes.

Key words.

cell phones, text messaging, misbehavior, challenge, teacher-student relationship

Teachers are facing a significant challenge in dealing with the use of cell phones, especially texting, in schools. There is a wide variation in the rules governing their usage among different school buildings and districts. Cheating is a particularly concerning issue, as students have been caught taking photos of exams and sharing them with friends who will be taking the same test later. To prevent cheating and other forms of misconduct, schools have implemented various regulations on the use of cell phones. Some schools have banned phones with cameras altogether, and others have prohibited students from bringing phones to school. The most common rule is for phones to be turned off and out of sight, and some schools extend this rule to include all electronic devices. While some schools allow students to have phones in their backpacks or lockers, they are usually not allowed to use them during school hours, except for emergencies. Other schools may allow limited phone use, such as during outdoor activities or lunch breaks.

When students break the rules on cell phone use, their phones are often confiscated. For a first offense, the teacher may return the phone at the end of the day, but repeated violations result in longer confiscation periods and may require a parent or guardian to retrieve the phone from the principal's office. Some schools

even resort to suspending students, even for a first offense. Cell phones have become the biggest challenge to maintaining discipline for many teachers, as they have led to inappropriate photos and videos being taken in private areas and shared, sometimes publicly. Text messaging has become a major activity during restroom breaks, replacing smoking as a subversive behavior.

Approximately 66% of teenagers own a cell phone. As a reflection of this trend, there are websites that provide students with instructions on how to use their phones in school without getting caught. While some teachers have embraced cell phones and suggest incorporating them into lessons, such as using text messaging for assignment reminders, others advocate for a fair use policy that allows responsible cell phone use. Here are some tips that may assist in addressing this issue in your classroom:

- To ensure that both students and parents are aware of the cell phone policies, it's important to communicate the rules clearly from the beginning of the school year. This can be done by posting the rules on a bulletin board or on the school's website. Some teachers also provide a handout to students that outlines the rules and the consequences of violating them. This helps to prevent misuse of cell phones in school.

- It's important to clearly explain to parents why cell phone rules are necessary. This can be done by emphasizing how the use of phones in class can be disruptive and negatively impact their child's learning. Additionally, it's important to highlight the potential for cheating that can occur when cell phones are allowed in class. By communicating these reasons to parents, they can better understand the importance of enforcing cell phone rules in schools.

- In schools where phones are allowed, some teachers have students check their phones as they enter the classroom. To ensure their safety, it's recommended that phones are placed in a locked box with students' names on them, and returned at the end of class. This policy may be easier to enforce with younger students. It's important to consistently and strictly enforce any policies that have been announced regarding cell phone use. It's also advisable to avoid giving out your personal cell phone number as it may lead to prank messages at all hours of the day. There are other methods of communication that can be used to contact you.

In conclusion, consistently enforcing these policies is key to their effectiveness. Teachers should be firm but fair in enforcing the rules, and should provide clear consequences for any violations. Finally, it's important for teachers to establish clear lines of communication with their students, without giving out personal cell phone numbers. Other methods of communication, such as email or school

messaging systems, can be used to effectively communicate with students and their parents.

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